

Challenges of Western Education in Contemporary Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This paper is designed to investigate challenges of Western Education in Contemporary Nigeria. The paper identified that right from abnatio, Western Education, past and present are nothing to right home about in terms of education. The work stressed on the policies and programme that are geared towards Qualitative education which is a clarion call to suicide in the educational sector. The paper went further to discuss that the policies and programmes made in Nigerian education negates the right educational principles and sustainability. The study discussed that some educational experts in the field have made frantic efforts towards writing of journals, publications, seminars on education to intimate Government at the top on the steps to adopt in making educational sector in Nigeria flourish, but, all their efforts was unable to see the light of the day due to government negligence in issues bordering on education in Nigeria. The paper frowned at the government decisions in fixing unprofessionals in certain positions of trust in educational sector to pilot the affairs of education in Nigerian, instead of professionals. The paper condemns poor funding, obnoxious policies, lack of manpower, nepotism and negligence occasioned by Nigeria government towards education. The paper believes that achieving good education hinges on jumping the hurdles of corruption, negligence of government and weak political leadership. The discussion was rounded up by concluding that to claim victory in Western Education, the people in educational sector must change their mindset and place education in front burner. The study hoped that we can make change that will enhance education in Nigeria for the betterment of the citizens.

Keywords: Challenges, Western Education, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

A nation or country cannot stand without education. Education remains the key to national development. Education is the engine room of every successful nation (Ada, 2020). Therefore, for a country to be recognized, their must be strong educational existence in line with peoples expectations. "Education" as the bedrock of human existence, plays a vital role in changing the narrative of a nation and ensure all round progress in the society and institutions.

Chile (2019) stated that Western Education Contemporary Nigeria cannot stand the test of time because of numerous challenges, ranging from wrong policies, programmes, poor funding, wrong placement of

staff, lack of manpower, nepotism, strike and bad leadership which stands tall in Western Education. Education in Nigeria lacks proper coordination due to inability of government to understand the value and its consequences. The hallmark of education has been destroyed by government because of negligence on issues bordering on education enhancement, promotion and value. Best (2018) posited that education in Nigeria can survive if the key players accept to come to round table discussions with people and agree to accept their mistakes and thereby discuss on the way forward. The growth of education is in our hand and the downfall of it is equally in our hand (Chukes, 2021). The sustainability of education and making it a paradise requires understanding, wisdom and collective idea.

Pascal, D. (2019), stated that education is the only tool that can change the faith of a country. Education instill consciousness, peace and knowledge that assist in building a United and peaceful co-existence. Education in Nigeria is a gateway for staff and students strike, lack of manpower, poor funding, poor package, nepotism and cultism etc. Education in Nigeria lacks the strength, willingness and courage to operate optimally and cannot afford needed stability for education to thrive in line with peoples expectation.

Education in Nigeria suffers a lot of setback on the needed ingredients or tools to function effectively. Staff in educational sector in Nigeria are discouraged and cannot be bold to talk good of Western Education because of ill-treatment meted on them.

Education remains the livewire of every successful nation and Government must retrace their steps in ensuring proper funding, adequate manpower, conducive environment for learning, better package for staff, good policies, implementation of favourable programmes and cordial relationship with their counterparts in the educational sector.

Charles (2020), opined that a genuine system of education should yield some distinctive value systems, which must be identical with that of society. As a social institution, education is invented by man to satisfy social needs. These needs however, differ from one society to another and from time to time. In this regard, the role, direction and character of education is a function of the prevalent philosophy of life and circumstances operative in any society or nation at any point in time. Therefore, education is supposed to bring about certain skills and attitudes that are desirable in the society.

IMPORTANCE OF WESTERN EDUCATION IN CONTEMPORARY NIGERIA

Education is the very essential for the development of a nation. This is shown in Amanda (2020) as follows:

1. It promotes values and attitudes of a developed nation.
2. It enhances national unity.
3. It promotes peaceful – co-existences of a nation and ensure rapid development.
4. It reduces reckless spending of nations economy or resources.
5. Education provides people with knowledge that is essential for national development.
6. Education creates awareness of our responsibilities to inculcate values and balances our lives.
7. Education establishes maturity, understanding and knowledge of what is happening around so with this knowledge, one understands the actual meaning of himself and herself as a citizen.
8. It shapes people mind and heart for its past and present to ensure co-operative and future nation.
9. Education remains a burwart of a nation and an instrument looked upon as a controlling events.

CONCEPT OF EDUCATION

Daniel (2017), defines education as the process by which every society attempts to preserve and upgrade the accumulated knowledge, skills, and attitudes in its cultural setting and heritage in order to foster and guarantee its survival. Again, Damjuma (2020), asserted that “education is that which prepares a man to perform justly, skillfully and magnanimously all the offices either in war or in peace”. Ben (2015), sees education as a process of integration through which the individual is helped to attain development of his potentials and maximum activation when necessary. Vipene (2015) defines education as “the shaping of behavior or modification of behaviours of the individual for adequate adjustment in the society.

Baddeley (2021), defines education as the avenue by which society through schools, colleges, universities and other institutions transmits to reality. Education is equally what transpired to us from the day we are born to the world and the day we die. Therefore, it remains life-long endeavour. Education is the community's means of nurturing personal growth. Tobin (2010), education is the aggregate of all the processes by which a child or young adult develop the abilities, attitude and other forms of behaviours that are positive values to the society in which he lives. Education in Nigeria embraces knowledge, civilization, discipline, and remains a valid body of organized knowledge that inculcates training and right upbringing of the peoples and society.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF WESTERN EDUCATION IN CONTEMPORARY NIGERIA

The aim of Western Education in Contemporary Nigeria according to National Policy on education (FGW, 2014), is to inculcate national consciousness and national unity, values and attitudes for the survival of the individuals in the society (UBEC, 2009).

1. **Free Education:** Free education which is enshrined in the National Policy has been neglected and politicized because of selfish Interest of our political leaders. The citizens were barred from their democratic right due to improper planning and wrong policy implementation.
2. **A just and equalitarian society:** A just and equalitarian society is a society that permits fairness, equity and justice. It is also a society where merits takes precedence over mediocrity. An equalitarian society ensures equal right of the citizens.
3. **A united strong and self-reliant nations:** Unity strength and self-reliance is the national interest of Nigeria. Self-reliance is the key for any nation that want to grow.

CHALLENGES OF WESTERN EDUCATION IN CONTEMPORARY NIGERIA

Okwuku (2019) states the followings as the challenges:

1. **Poor Remuneration:** Poor income has created lack of interest among staff in the educational sector and encourages stealing among the heads in order to meet their target in life. Poor package to staff in educational sector speaks volume and unaddressed in Nigeria institutions.
2. **Poor Facilities:** Lack of provision for facilities in educational sector has become a source of concern in educational sector in Nigeria. Such as practical laboratory, library, school desks, instructional materials and recreational centres, has negatively impacted in teaching and learning.
3. **Incessant Strike:** Strike is a period of time when an organized group of employees of a company or institutions of learning stops working because of disagreement over payment or conditions of service. Strike is a deliberate stoppage of work by workers in order to put pressure on their employer to accede to their demands (Obindu & Kelechi, 2021; Ahmed, 2014). During strike actions academic activities are put on a hold, and when students resume classes there is usually a rush of learning activities as a result, many students are poorly prepared for exams and movement to the next level.

The ASUU strike which lasted for eight months grounded academic activities of federal and state universities in the country. While the strike lasted it resulted to court action where the federal government took ASUU to court. This was indeed an ugly development in our educational system. To crown it all, the federal government encouraged and sponsored a parallel Academic Staff Union of Universities to fight ASUU.

4. **School Drop-Out:** Drop-out is defined as premature termination of an educational cycle. That is to say that a student leaves school before the end of the final year of the educational cycle in which he/she is enrolled. This is one major problem facing Nigerian educational system. Many students leaves school because of the hash economic environment, income level of parents, cultism in school, repeated academic failures, difficult lecturers, the thought of employment after school and the desire of become rich overnight etc.
5. **The Problem of Policy Implementation:** A policy is an overall guide that gives the general limits and direction in which administration action will take place (Okoroma, 2016). Our educational system has witnessed various educational policies in the last four decades. What may

seem like a good policy, is changed to another and poorly executed. This is not healthy to our educational system, is further reduced the educational standard. Also, a gap usually existed between policy formulation and implementation. Good planning that can facilitate effective implementation of policies ought to consider such factors as the planning environment, social environment, political environment, and financial and statistical challenges but in most policy implementations, these are not considered. Poor policy implementation leads to policy somersault which describes the state of the Nigerian educational system.

The policy that brought in the 6-3-3-4 policy for example really meant good for the educational system of Nigeria. Under this structure, pupils at the primary level will spend six years. Students at junior secondary level (JSS 1-3) three years and those at the senior secondary level (SSS 1-3) will undergo three years training. When this policy was introduced, most secondary schools were equipped with various kinds of workshops and tools. But today that huge investment is not there in our schools. The greatest problem this policy had was that there were no enough teachers with such technical skills to teach and train the students. Today the junior and the senior secondary schools are seen as two different schools in the same compound where students only respect teachers from their section.

6. **Funding/Inadequate Budgetary Allocation:** The problem of funding is one major challenge confronting the educational system in Nigeria. Nigeria is one of such countries that is yet to allocate 26 percent of her budgetary allocation to education as recommended by the United Nations (UNESCO). The 2023 budget has a total figure of £21.83trn, only £470bn was allocated to universities and other tertiary institutions which is below what is given to one federal ministry. This goes a long way to affect the quality of education delivery in Nigeria. The federal government is yet to learn from their past mistakes and what lead to the 2022 strike action of ASUU that lasted for eighteen months.
7. **Lack of Manpower:** The ratio of teachers to pupils is such that, there are more students have few teachers. Therefore the work load for the teacher is very high. Also in more schools a single teacher will teaches in almost all the classes due to lack of teachers. These has crippled educational sector due to failure of government to employ people that would assist keep the ball rolling. The educational sector is calling for manpower to enhance teaching and learning in Nigerian education.
8. Wrong placement of people into positions in educational sector have suffered a serious setback because of government decisions in allowing unprofessional to occupy certain positions in educational sector.

WAY FORWARD

Pascal (2019), states the followings as the way forward:

1. Government should be sensitive in matters related to education because of its value in the development of a nation and citizens.
2. Government should come up with favourable policies that will enhance education in Nigeria and ensure its implementation.
3. Government should stop politicking on the issues bordering on educational growth and development in Nigeria.
4. Government should provide adequate facilities for learning and teaching to thrive.
5. Government should stop diverting funds meant for building and promoting education in Nigeria into frivolous things.

CONCLUSION

Education in Nigeria are in comatose and cannot meet the needed requirements of people in the society. The decay in Nigeria educational system is alarming thereby calls for urgent attention to avert the looming total brake down, which was as a result of government negligence and wrong policies and programmes. Education need proper overhauling in order to stem the hope and people's expectations. Our

political leaders should encourage good implementations and programmes that will sustain education in Nigeria. The sustenance of it should begin from listening to people and take viable steps to remedy years of wrongs and injustices.

SUGGESTIONS

In order to achieve optimally in education

1. Government should reel out fantastic policies and programmes that must begin to build enduring institutions bigger and more powerful than the leadership.
2. Leaders in education sector, must be accountable to the people and these members of the ruling class who derive joy in stealing public fund, marginalization and underdevelopment must be made to face the full wrath of the law, if they go contrary.
3. Resource control; individual should be allowed to know how government spends their money.
4. The judiciary should be made stronger as to enable them prosecute any defaulter in the educational sector that aired in law.

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